

Reproducibility Analysis of the Workflow and Results of the CosRec-Model

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ABSTRACT

Reproducibility is an important aspect of scientific work, but it has been shown that many study results are not reproducible, or that the presented workflows are not even re-executable. To this effect, we chose a recently published article that proposed a novel approach to sequential recommendation, tried to reproduce the workflow and investigated the results. We were able to show that the workflow itself can be very easily reproduced. Furthermore, we obtained very similar results to those presented in the article when we used the data provided by the authors; statistical tests confirmed this observation. However, upon closer investigation of the data-preparation protocol, we found that we could not fully reproduce the identical training and test data as used by the authors. While this had almost no effect on the results obtained for one of the datasets, the results for the second dataset differed substantially from the ones presented in the paper. With that in mind, we consider this work to be reproducible for just one of the datasets, and conclude that for the successful reproduction of the results of the second dataset, a more detailed description of the data-preparation protocol would be needed.

KEYWORDS

reproducibility, sequential recommendation, convolutional neural networks, preprocessing

1 INTRODUCTION

Reproducibility is an important aspect of every scientific work and publication. If the work conducted is created in a way that facilitates the reproduction by others, it is possible to confirm the obtained results and to build on them in further work. This enhances scientific working in general.

Unfortunately, many studies are not or not completely reproducible. For example, a study from 2018 showed that out of 106 analyzed articles 78 contained at least one result that could not be reproduced. Out of those 106 articles, only five met the highest standards of self-contained reproducibility, which encompasses public availability of all the data used for the article as well as no dependence on additional input to reproduce the results. [1] Therefore, in the framework of the course "Experiment Design for Data Science" of the Technical University Vienna, we chose a recent publication and tested, if and how well the results obtained are reproducible.

There are many approaches to Recommender Systems. The more traditional one tries to capture a user's global taste based on their previous actions as a whole. The paper by Yan et al. [3] on the other hand follows the sequential recommendation approach, which also takes the order of the user's historical actions into account. Previously Markov-chains and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) were used to accomplish this task. In their paper, Yan et al. propose a new

method that uses a special encoding scheme and two-dimensional convolutional neural networks for sequential recommendation (CosRec). The authors claim that their new method outperforms conventional methods, as well as state of the art sequence-based approaches on two public datasets. The datasets in question are the *MovieLens*-dataset, which is based on data generated by a movie-rating website, as well as the *Gowalla*-dataset, which contains data from a location-based social-networking site.

2 METHODS AND IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 General Setup

The code, together with preprocessed training- and test data, is available on GitHub. ¹ After cloning the repository and installing one more dependency (PyTorch; this is clearly stated in the repository's README) the code runs without any further adjustments, provided that a GPU is available.

The GPU requirement, however, might be a challenge for researchers with a "usual" notebook. Therefore, we first used Google Colab ² for our investigations, which provides a limited amount of free GPU time. This worked quite well for the smaller *MovieLens* dataset, where the duration of the training phase averaged at around 90 minutes. But using the *Gowalla* dataset posed quite a challenge, as the training took considerably longer (about 6.5 hours). This caused frequent early cancellations of the training process, as the Colab notebook was shut down due to their user interaction policy and lack of background execution capabilities in the free version.

Upon closer inspection of the source code, we discovered that the weights of the trained neural network were stored at the end of every second training epoch (40 in total). Interestingly, no functionality for loading these weights was implemented in the code available in the author's GitHub repository. We decided to implement this functionality as it would give us the ability to restart a cancelled training session from a known checkpoint. Unfortunately, even after implementing this functionality, training the network with the *Gowalla* dataset turned out to be impractical on Colab, due to the many manual steps required to complete the training of the network. Thus, our next step was to move the Python notebooks from Colab to Kaggle ³. There we created a new dataset instance, containing the data from the author's repository. In addition to that, all auxiliary scripts were converted to so-called utility scripts (which can be imported into a notebook). After this setup process, we were able to run the main notebook and start the training session from within the notebook. On Kaggle, it is also possible to

¹<https://github.com/zxxslp/CosRec>

²<https://colab.research.google.com/>

³<https://www.kaggle.com/>

run a notebook in the background, thus we were now also able to complete the multi-hour training of the Gowalla dataset.

2.2 Reproduction of the Data Sets

The GitHub repository contains a data-folder with some already preprocessed training- and test data, for each of the two data sets. The authors claimed to have followed the same preprocessing procedure as in Caser[2]: The presence of a review or rating is interpreted as implicit feedback, as the user obviously interacted with this item. The timestamps of the reviews are used to sort the interactions, and all users and items with less than 5 (ML-1M) or 15 (Gowalla) interactions are discarded. Then, the first 80% of each user’s ratings are used as training data, and the last 20% as test data.

We repeated those preprocessing steps as described in the paper, in order to see whether we would receive the same training- and test set as used in the repository. Although the described preprocessing seems straightforward, during implementation, we encountered some details that were ambiguously explained in the paper:

- The authors claim to "discard users and items with fewer than 5 and 15 actions for ML-1M and Gowalla respectively". It is not clear whether (a) in both data sets, users with fewer than 5 and items with fewer than 15 actions were discarded, or (b) in ML-1M, users and items with fewer than 5 actions and in Gowalla, users and items with fewer than 15 actions were discarded. Fortunately, this was explained unambiguously in the Caser-paper [2], the correct interpretation is (b).
- After firstly discarding those users with too few actions, then those items, there could be new users that now have too few actions. It is not clear whether the discarding should be repeated in a loop, until for real all users and all items have the least number of actions. We went for the loop approach.

After repeating those steps, we found that the IDs from our reproduced data don’t match those of the repository data. This is not necessarily a problem, but it prevents from an immediate comparison of the obtained data sets, as the data sets will not be identical.

The paper presents some statistics of the training data. In order to compare the data sets, we re-computed those statistics of the repository data, and also computed them for our reproduced data, see Table 1. The statistics for the ML-1M data set fit perfectly. The statistics for the Gowalla data set, on the other hand, don’t fit; our reproduced training set is around 5 times as big as the one used in the repository.

Data	Origin	Users	Items	Avg. #act per user	Avg. #act per item	Actions
ML-1M	Repo	6.0K	3.4K	165.50	292.06	0.993M
ML-1M	repr	6.0K	3.4K	165.50	292.63	1.000M
Gowalla	Repo	13.1K	14.0K	40.74	38.12	0.533M
Gowalla	repr	66.9K	75.4K	43.58	37.32	2.81M
Gowalla	repr (2)	9.1K	15.5K	58.34	34.26	0.533M

Table 1: Statistics of the data sets

Due to this, we created another Gowalla data set, in which at least the number of actions fits to the repository data. We tested

the CosRec algorithm on this smaller Gowalla set, as well as on the reproduced ML-1M set. We compared those results to the results of the repository data, see section 3.

We encountered two more things we were not able to explain:

- The repository contains two sub-folders in the data folder, *test/* and *validation/*, both containing *train.txt* and *test.txt*, respectively. In the code, however, only the folder *test/* is used; *validation/* appears neither in the code, nor is it mentioned in the paper.
- The statistics of the data sets, as presented in Table 1, were not completely correct. After re-computing the statistics, we encountered slightly different values for the last two columns of each data set. We assume, that the authors draw the first three columns from the data sets and computed the last two columns based on simple arithmetic on the rounded values; this is how one would obtain the presented values.

3 RESULTS

The paper contains results to the algorithm’s mean average precision (MAP), Precision@N and Recall@N, for $N \in \{1, 5, 10\}$, for both data sets. For each score, however, only one value is provided, instead of a distribution. It is not clear whether this value stems from a single run, or if it is the mean of multiple runs, and if so, of how many runs.

3.1 Results for the preprocessed Data Sets

In order to compare the values from our reproduction to the reported values from the paper, we conducted 10 runs on each of the two already-preprocessed datasets with different seeds for randomness. Because the seed used in the paper is not published, we were not able to do a single run that yielded the exact same results as the ones presented in the paper. Due to the nature of the data (the test train split has to be along the time axis so that CosRec can predict the last 20% on the basis of the first 80%), we could not reshuffle the data.

After obtaining the results from the 10 runs, we conducted a t-test to see if the data from the paper and our results stem from the same distribution. Unfortunately, the fact that the paper only did one run means that the unbiased estimator for this sample is undefined as the sample size is 1.

There are two different formulas for two-sample t-tests with different sample sizes, one for similar and one for unequal variances. Because of the undefined estimator, we are unable to use the formula for different variances, but the formula for similar sample sizes works, since the undefined estimator gets cancelled out. (For the following formulas we use the values $n_1 = 1$ and $n_2 = 10$)

$$\begin{aligned}
 t &= \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{(n_1-1)s_1^2 + (n_2-1)s_2^2}{n_1+n_2-2} \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)}} \\
 &= \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{0s_1^2 + 9s_2^2}{9} \left(\frac{1}{1} + \frac{1}{10} \right)}} = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{s_2 \sqrt{\frac{11}{10}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

We can see that this is the same formula that we would get if we used the formula for different variances, but set the variances to be the same. ($s_1 = s_2$)

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{11s_2^2}{10}}} = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{s_2\sqrt{\frac{11}{10}}}$$

With this formula, we were able to compute a test statistic and the corresponding p-values. As seen in Table 2, most of the result values are similar and therefore result in high p-values. From this, we can conclude that there is no statistically significant difference in the results from the paper and our results except for the *Precision @ 5* for the ML-1M dataset, as usually, a statistically significant difference is concluded for a p-value of $p < 0.05$. The explanation for this still could be the inherent randomness when dealing with such small sample sizes or a typo by the original author.

3.2 Results for the reproduced Data Sets

We further used our reproduced data sets, which were prepared as explained in subsection 2.2, as training data for the CosRec algorithm, in order to compare their results to the ones that were derived from the preprocessed data. We performed another t-test on the results, like in subsection 3.1, the results are presented in Table 3.

For ML-1M, the obtained results for the reproduced data sets are similar to those for the preprocessed data. The t-tests showed, that MAP, Precision @ 1, Precision @ 5 and Recall @ 1 are not statistically significantly different between the two data sets; the other values are. This could, however, also be explained with the small sample size.

For the Gowalla data set, on the other hand, the results for the reproduced data sets are significantly worse than the ones for the preprocessed data. The statistical tests (that were actually only performed for the sake of completeness) also showed, that the results should stem from two entirely different distributions.

4 CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In general, the authors did a good job in making their work reproducible. The code itself runs out of the box without any adjustments required. Furthermore, all data needed to reproduce the results is provided as well, although there are some uncertainties on how the open-source data was preprocessed.

As a GPU is needed to run the code, the code can most likely not run on a usual computer. However, in order to perform deep learning, GPUs are nowadays needed in most of the cases, and thanks to services like Google Colab or Kaggle, the code can still be run by everybody interested in a topic.

Our experiments confirmed the results presented in the original paper, when using the provided, preprocessed data. The obtained performance metrics were very close to those presented in the paper, statistical tests confirmed that the presented values could actually stem from the same distribution as our results. However, it should be taken into account, that our results rely on a comparably low number of runs: We performed 10 runs on the preprocessed data and 5 runs on our reproduced data. This was due to a lack of resources on our side.

The explanation of the preprocessing for the data sets, on the other hand, is not complete. One of the data sets, ML-1M, was most likely successfully reproduced by us, as the data statistics are the same and the results after training are very similar to the ones provided in the paper. Due to the changed IDs, however, we can not be completely sure about this. The other data set, Gowalla, could not be reproduced by us. We did not find the reasons for the differences, the description in the paper was not clear enough. The assumption, that the ML-1M data set was successfully reproduced, in contrast to the Gowalla data set, is further amplified by the performance results of the CosRec algorithm on those data sets: The results for ML-1M are very similar to those from the preprocessed data sets, the results for the reproduced Gowalla data are way worse. The latter is not completely surprising, as already the statistics in Table 1 showed, that we were not able to recreate the preprocessed data set.

5 ACCOMPANYING RESOURCES

The source code of the modified CosRec implementation, as well as the code we used to re-create the datasets from their original sources has been made available under an open-source license on GitHub.⁴⁵

REFERENCES

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⁴<https://github.com/yozone/CosRec>

⁵<https://github.com/nweibrecht/Experiment-Design>

		reproduced results				
		paper result	avg	std	t statistic	p-value
ML-1M	MAP	0.1883	0.1884	0.0006	-0.22	0.830
	Precision @ 1	0.3308	0.3256	0.0046	1.08	0.308
	Precision @ 5	0.2831	0.2776	0.0016	3.22	0.010
	Precision @ 10	0.2493	0.2469	0.0012	1.81	0.103
	Recall @ 1	0.0202	0.0202	0.0005	0.07	0.946
	Recall @ 5	0.0843	0.0827	0.0007	2.10	0.066
	Recall @ 10	0.1438	0.1422	0.0010	1.52	0.162
Gowalla	MAP	0.0980	0.0980	0.0004	0.05	0.962
	Precision @ 1	0.2135	0.2099	0.0029	1.19	0.263
	Precision @ 5	0.1190	0.1177	0.0007	1.73	0.118
	Precision @ 10	0.0884	0.0817	0.0169	0.38	0.715
	Recall @ 1	0.0337	0.0339	0.0004	-0.47	0.647
	Recall @ 5	0.0890	0.0896	0.0005	-1.25	0.245
	Recall @ 10	0.1305	0.1291	0.0010	1.34	0.215

Table 2: Results of 10 runs with different seeds on the preprocessed data sets compared to the original results

		results on preprocessed data			
		avg	std	t statistic	p-value
ML-1M	MAP	0.1889	0.0006	-1.3173	0.2089
	Precision @ 1	0.3261	0.0027	-0.2313	0.8204
	Precision @ 5	0.2793	0.0019	-1.7987	0.0937
	Precision @ 10	0.2498	0.0010	-4.3718	0.0006
	Recall @ 1	0.0197	0.0003	2.0316	0.0616
	Recall @ 5	0.0802	0.0007	5.9951	0.0000
	Recall @ 10	0.1396	0.0011	4.6754	0.0004
Gowalla	MAP	0.0325	0.0001	353.58	0.000
	Precision @ 1	0.0583	0.0014	109.16	0.000
	Precision @ 5	0.0405	0.0008	179.81	0.000
	Precision @ 10	0.0328	0.0005	6.37	0.000
	Recall @ 1	0.0101	0.0002	119.78	0.000
	Recall @ 5	0.0328	0.0008	167.69	0.000
	Recall @ 10	0.0519	0.0006	153.05	0.000

Table 3: Results of 5 runs with different seeds on the reproduced data sets, t-statistic and p-value for comparison with results on the preprocessed data sets